

Review

The Therapeutic and Methodological Aspects of Moxibustion for Breech Presentation: An Analysis of Randomised Controlled Trials.

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Abstract

Introduction: Breech presentation, which occurs in approximately 3% of deliveries, is associated with a higher risk of complications like birth asphyxia and umbilical cord prolapse. Moxibustion, a traditional East Asian therapy, involves warming specific acupuncture points with ignited *Artemisia* to promote the circulation of *qi* and blood flow. Its modern effects may include thermal stimulation, infrared radiation, and the biological activities of mugwort components, which can dilate blood vessels, increase blood flow, and improve immune function.

Methods: This review aims to analyse the efficacy and clinical methodologies of moxibustion for breech presentation by synthesising evidence from randomised controlled trials published between 2010 and July 2025. The search was conducted on PubMed and SciELO using keywords related to the intervention, condition, and study design. Included studies were RCTs that investigated moxibustion for cephalic version and reported on clinical outcomes, while systematic reviews, meta-analyses, and observational studies were excluded. Data on study design, population, intervention, control methods, and outcomes were qualitatively synthesised.

Results: The analysis included four randomised controlled trials, with two studies finding that moxibustion was effective and two others finding no differences. The studies showed significant variations in their clinical methodologies. While all trials used the BL67 acupuncture point, the procedures differed. Treatment duration and frequency also varied.

Conclusion: The current evidence on moxibustion for breech presentation is inconsistent due to a lack of methodological standardisation across trials. However, the most rigorous study in this review found moxibustion to be an effective intervention, a finding supported by other systematic reviews and meta-analyses. The conflicting results highlight the need for a more standardised approach to the clinical application of moxibustion in future research to establish it as a reliable therapeutic option.

Keywords: Obstetrics; Breech Presentation; Cephalic Version; Moxibustion; Traditional Chinese Medicine; Complementary Therapies.

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1. Introduction

Breech presentation is defined as the fetal position where the buttocks, knees, or feet are nearest to the cervix, with the head located in the fundal region of the uterus ¹. This

condition is observed in approximately 3% of deliveries and is associated with an increased risk of complications²⁻⁴. These complications can include a delay in delivery and a higher incidence of birth asphyxia due to factors like umbilical cord prolapse and head entrapment².

Determining the most effective management strategy for women presenting with a term breech foetus is a topic that is still under active discussion⁵.

In 2000, the Term Breech Trial (TBT) Collaborative Group published a study that led to a significant shift in the management of breech presentations, finding a lower risk of serious neonatal morbidity and mortality in the planned cesarean section group compared to the planned vaginal birth group⁶. This prompted major organisations to recommend planned cesarean section for all singleton breech presentations^{5,7}.

Despite its influence, the TBT had several weaknesses, including a lack of adherence to strict vaginal birth criteria and suboptimal labour management⁸⁻¹⁰. A follow-up analysis at two years found no reduction in the risk of death or neurodevelopmental delay in children, raising questions about the trial's true implications¹¹. Furthermore, the study noted that the risk of maternal morbidity was lowest with vaginal birth and highest with cesarean section after labour^{11,12}.

Subsequent studies provided further insight. A study by Hartnack Tharin *et al.*¹³ showed that while cesarean section rates for breech deliveries increased, the decrease in perinatal mortality was smaller than what the TBT suggested. As well, Vlemmix *et al.*¹⁴ found that while elective cesarean section rates rose and perinatal mortality decreased, it would take 338 cesarean section deliveries to prevent one perinatal death. Moreover, van Dillen *et al.*¹⁵ also estimated a higher risk of severe maternal morbidity with elective cesarean section compared to an attempted vaginal delivery.

In response to these discussions, some guidelines were revised, and planned vaginal delivery is considerably reasonable for selected women⁵.

Given the potential complications of both breech delivery and cesarean section, achieving a cephalic version remains a crucial goal. Therefore, developing and utilising complementary techniques is vital to improve outcomes.

Moxibustion, a widely used East Asian traditional therapy¹⁶, involves warming acupuncture points with ignited herbal materials, primarily processed *Artemisia*^{17,18}.

The traditional theory behind moxibustion is that it promotes the circulation of *qi* and blood by warming acupoints¹⁹. From a modern perspective, researchers believe its effects may be due to thermal stimulation, radiation, and the biological activity of compounds found in *Artemisia* leaves and moxa smoke^{19,20}. *Artemisia* contains flavonoids, phenylpropanoids, and other components possessing anti-inflammatory and antioxidant potential²¹⁻²⁴. Moxibustion appears to work by dilating blood vessels, increasing local blood flow, and relaxing muscles. Additionally, the burning moxa emits infrared radiation that penetrates the skin, which may promote healing, improve circulation, and boost immune function²⁵⁻²⁸. Despite these hypotheses, its exact mechanism of action has not yet been fully clarified¹⁸.

Traditionally, moxibustion has been used to treat a wide variety of conditions^{19,29}, and recent randomised controlled trials have explored its effectiveness for several conditions³⁰.

Therefore, this study aims to briefly analyse randomised controlled trials on the efficacy of moxibustion for breech presentation, exploring the clinical methodologies employed in those studies.

2. Methods

This review was conducted to synthesise current evidence on the methodologies of moxibustion for cephalic version in breech presentation. We searched for randomised controlled trials published in the last 15 years (from 2010 to July 2025) in English, Portuguese, Spanish, French, or Chinese. The search was performed on electronic databases, including PubMed and SciELO.

Our search strategy included a combination of keywords related to the intervention (“moxibustion”, “acupuncture”, “moxa”), the condition (“breech presentation”, “cephalic version”), and the study design (“randomized controlled trial”, “RCT”).

Studies were included if they met the following criteria: They were a randomised controlled trial. They investigated the use of moxibustion, either alone or in combination with other interventions, to achieve cephalic version in breech presentation. They were published between 2010 and July 2025. They reported on clinical outcomes such as fetal position at delivery or rate of external cephalic version.

Studies were excluded if they were systematic reviews, meta-analyses, case reports, or observational studies.

Two authors screened the titles and abstracts of all identified studies. Full-text articles were then retrieved and reviewed based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Any disagreements were resolved through discussion with a third author until consensus was reached.

Data from the included studies were extracted and qualitatively synthesised. The extracted data included the study objective, patient population, intervention and control methods, and key clinical outcomes. This qualitative synthesis allowed us to provide an overview of the current evidence on moxibustion's effects on breech presentation and analyse the clinical methodological aspects.

3. Results

Our analysis integrated findings from four separate randomised controlled trials, each addressing the topic. The studies varied slightly in design, with the characteristics summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Main research designs of the included studies.

Study	Occultation	Control	Location
Do <i>et al.</i> ³¹	Non-blinded	Usual care	Single-center
Sananes <i>et al.</i> ³²	Single-blinded	Sham	Single-center
Bue <i>et al.</i> ³³	Non-blinded	Usual care	Single-center
Vas <i>et al.</i> ³⁴	Non-blinded	Sham and usual care	Multicenter

4. Discussion

4.1. Efficacy

Do *et al.* ³¹ conducted a feasibility randomised controlled trial, focusing on the use of moxibustion for cephalic version. While the study was not powered to detect a statistical difference, the results showed a trend toward an increase in cephalic version at delivery for women in the moxibustion group compared to the usual care group. The authors also noted a trend toward greater success with external cephalic version (ECV) in the moxibustion group. No side effects were reported. Despite the preliminary design with a small sample size, the results and the positive response from both women and healthcare professionals suggested that a larger trial on the effectiveness of moxibustion was feasible and that the technique should be explored further.

To address the limitations of using moxibustion in a clinical setting, as hospitals often do not allow it due to smoke and fire alarm facilities, Sananes *et al.* ³² modified the technique. Instead of using moxa rolls, they heated the tip of the inserted acupuncture needle directly with a lighter until the patient felt a sensation of warmth. Technically, no moxibustion was used; however, this modification allows practitioners to achieve a similar thermal effect directly on the acupuncture point without the use of a burning stick. As well, some studies observe that the smoke from moxibustion is the main reason for withdrawal in other studies on the topic ^{35,36}.

The study found that while the rate of cephalic presentations was higher in the thermal acupuncture group (37.7%) than in the sham group (28.7%), this difference was not statistically significant after adjusting for parity (OR 1.47, 0.84–2.42). Importantly, the authors suggested that future studies should use stratified randomisation for nulliparous and parous patients.

Making the suggested stratification, Bue *et al.*³³ found similar results in their randomised clinical trial on the effectiveness of moxibustion for breech presentation.

The results showed that, after a 16-day trial, the moxibustion group did not achieve a significant difference in the incidence of breech position compared to the control group (usual care) for both nulliparous (RR = 1.17, 95% CI: 0.77-1.76) and parous (RR = 1.0, 95% CI: 0.69-1.46) women.

However, a three-arm, multicentre randomised controlled trial by Vas *et al.*³⁴ observed otherwise. The study found that true moxibustion was more effective than both sham moxibustion and usual care alone for correcting non-cephalic presentations. In the verum moxibustion group, 58.1% of full-term presentations were cephalic, compared to 43.4% in the sham group and 44.8% in the usual care group. The relative risk (RR) for cephalic presentation at birth was 1.34 (95% CI 1.05-1.70) when comparing true moxibustion to sham, and 1.29 (95% CI 1.02-1.64) when comparing it to usual care. The study reported no severe adverse effects.

Although the included clinical trials have shown conflicting results, the most well-designed trial (Vas *et al.*³⁴) presented favourable results regarding the use of moxibustion for breech presentation.

These results are aligned with the Cochrane systematic review by Coyle *et al.*³⁷, which found moderate-certainty evidence that moxibustion in addition to usual care reduces the chance of non-cephalic presentation at birth.

This correction of breech presentation benefited by moxibustion is also supported by other systematic reviews and meta-analyses^{38,39}.

4.2. Clinical methodology

To explore the effects of moxibustion for breech presentation, it is crucial to explore the methodologies applied in each study. Table 2 summarises those aspects according to the information available in the included studies.

Table 2. Moxibustion methodologies in the included studies.

Study	Do <i>et al.</i> ³¹	Sananes <i>et al.</i> ³²	Bue <i>et al.</i> ³³	Vas <i>et al.</i> ³⁴
Result	Favours moxibustion	No differences	No differences	Favours moxibustion
Procedure	Smokeless moxa stick one thumb width above the BL67 acupuncture point	Copper acupuncture needle heated by a lighter in the BL67 acupuncture point	Moxa stick at BL67 acupuncture point	Moxa stick 1.5-3 cm above the BL67 acupuncture point
Intervention duration	10 minutes on each foot with a total of 20 minutes	Applied fire to the needle until the patient feels a warm sensation. The procedure was repeated 3 times alternatively on each foot.	15-20 minutes	20 min alternated every 2 minutes or more often on both feet
Treatment frequency and duration	Twice a day (morning and evening) for ten days.	Three sessions over a period of 7 to 10 days.	Daily (preferably in the evening) for a minimum of 2 weeks and a maximum of 3 weeks.	Daily for two weeks.

The studies showed varying results, with two supporting moxibustion's effectiveness^{31,34} and two others finding no benefit^{32,33}.

These randomised clinical trials differed significantly in their study design (as shown in Table 1) and, more importantly, in their clinical application of moxibustion. For instance, two studies used a direct moxa stick^{33,34}, but only one specified the distance it should be held from the skin³⁴. Other trials used different methods entirely: one utilised a smokeless moxa stick³¹, while another replaced the moxa's heat with a lighter flame applied to an acupuncture needle³².

Figure 1 represents the different techniques.

Figure 1. Visual depiction of the three different methods applied in the included studies.

The use of traditional moxibustion vs smokeless moxibustion is an ongoing scientific debate with several studies supporting the benefits of using smokeless moxa⁴⁰⁻⁴². Interestingly, Chen *et al.*⁴² found that the highest radiation peak of new smokeless moxibustion, located at a wavelength of 3.75 μm , is similar to that of traditional moxibustion. The infrared spectral characteristics of both methods are also comparable, indicating that the new smokeless version has potential as an alternative. However, this new smokeless version has a particular addition of *Artemisia* leaf extract to the activated carbon column in order to retain the therapeutic aspects of the *Artemisia* leaf⁴².

On the other hand, and favouring homogeneity, all studies applied their respective procedures in the BL67 (*Zhiyin* 至陰[阴]) acupuncture point (Figure 2).

Figure 2. BL67 localisation. On the little toe, lateral to the distal phalanx, 0.1 f-cun proximal to the lateral corner of the toenail; at the intersection of the vertical line of the lateral side of the nail and the horizontal line of the base of the toenail ⁴³.

BL67 is the last acupuncture point of the *Taiyang* Bladder meridian of the foot. It is the *Jing* (well) point of the Bladder meridian. Its traditional use has several applications (Table 3).

Table 3. BL67 indications according to Zappol ⁴⁴.

BL67
One of the twelve <i>Jin</i> points. It can be used to treat a coma in first aid.
For the correction of the foetal position (using moxibustion).
In placenta retention due to prolonged labour.
For terminal neuritis, pain and numbness of the toe tip.

Supporting the traditional effects presented, a randomised controlled trial by Hamidzadeh *et al.* ⁴⁵ found that acupressure at this acupuncture point reduces the rate of caesarean sections by promoting foetal cephalic version.

Acupressure at BL67 may also be beneficial for decreasing labour pain during the active phase of the first stage of labour ⁴⁶.

Further comparing the studies, it is clear that there are significant differences in the duration and frequency of the moxibustion application.

Regarding the length of each session, all studies placed their duration between 15 and 20 minutes. However, Do *et al.* ³¹ and Vas *et al.* ³⁴ both had a relatively short overall treatment period of 10 days and two weeks, respectively, with daily application. Do *et al.* ³¹ specified a twice-daily frequency, whereas Vas *et al.* ³⁴ used a daily frequency.

Bue *et al.* ³³ had a longer treatment period, ranging from 2 weeks to 3 weeks, with daily application (despite some participants not completing the minimum 2 weeks).

Sananes *et al.* ³² stands out with a very different approach, using only three sessions over a 7- to 10-day period.

5. Final Remarks

While some studies have shown conflicting outcomes, a critical analysis of the methodologies reveals key factors that may explain the varying results.

This review found a lack of methodological consistency across the trials, which could account for the divergent findings. While all studies targeted the same BL67 acupuncture point, they varied significantly in the type of moxibustion used, ranging from traditional and smokeless moxa sticks to a lighter heating the acupuncture needle. Furthermore, the duration and frequency of the treatment were not standardised, with some studies using three sessions over a week and others using daily sessions for two to three weeks.

Despite these inconsistencies, the most methodologically sound trial included in this review (Vas *et al.*³⁴) found that moxibustion was more effective than both sham and usual care. This finding is reinforced by other systematic reviews and meta-analyses, which also support the use of moxibustion to reduce the rate of non-cephalic presentations at birth. The conflicting results, therefore, highlight the need for a more standardised approach to moxibustion research to better understand and confirm its efficacy.

6. Conclusions

The body of evidence on moxibustion for breech presentation is currently inconsistent. However, the most rigorous and best-designed study in this review found that moxibustion is an effective intervention, supported by systematic reviews and meta-analyses of the topic. The conflicting results from other trials highlight the need for a more standardised approach to the clinical application of moxibustion in future research. This would allow for a clearer understanding of its efficacy and help establish it as a reliable therapeutic option.

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